

“Journeying in Communion and Commitment” Pope Francis’ Visionary Response to the Climate Crisis in *Laudate Deum*

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Abstract

Laudate Deum (Praise God) is Pope Francis’ prophetic call-in response to the climate crisis. It offers insights into the current state of the global climate crisis, and the inadequacies of current responses, and proposes the way forward. He asks us to journey together in “communion and commitment” to reduce the negative human impact on the natural environment and to create a better environment for future generations. He invites us for a “pilgrimage of reconciliation,” “reconciliation with the world that shelters us” (LD 69). This paper attempts to unravel Pope Francis’ visionary response to the climate crisis in *Laudate Deum*.

Introduction

Laudate Deum (Praise God) is the sixth apostolic exhortation by Pope Francis, published on October 4, 2023.¹ It was released on the Feast of St Francis Assisi, and the opening of the Synod on Synodality, as a follow-up to his landmark 2015 encyclical on “Care for our Common Home,” *Laudato Si’*. *Laudato Si’* was written to engage the scientific, political, and religious communities, and summoned us all to a renewed commitment to “care for our common home,” and it was addressed to “every living person on this planet” (LS 3). Likewise, *Laudate Deum* is also addressed to “all people of goodwill on the climate crisis,” focusing more narrowly on the issue of climate change. It picks up pace by naming climate change as a crisis. It takes a look at what has happened since 2015 and what still needs to be done to prevent the impending dangers in the environment (cf. LD 2). On a basic level, *Laudate Deum* intends to “clarify and complete” the work begun in *Laudato Si’* (LD 4). Thus, eight years after *Laudato Si’* (LD 2), Pope Francis

reiterates his “heartfelt concerns about the care of our common home” (LD 2). For Pope Francis, it is an issue that profoundly touches human identity in its relationships, as well as the concrete survival of humanity in this world; an issue that concerns not a distant future, but a present reality that we are now grappling with. Therefore, he says, “Let us finally admit that it is a human and social problem on any number of levels. For this reason, it calls for involvement on the part of all” (LD 58).

Given the rapid worsening of the climate crisis since 2015, the tone of Pope Francis in *Laudate Deum* is rather a frustrated one, but he invites everyone to reflect upon the climate crisis with hope. He writes that “with the passage of time, I have realized that our responses have not been adequate, while the world in which we live is collapsing and may be nearing the breaking point” (LD 2). He also adds that “it is indubitable that the impact of climate change will increasingly prejudice the lives and families of many persons. We will feel its effects in the areas of healthcare, sources of employment, access to resources, housing, forced migrations, etc.” (LD 2). Thus, *Laudate Deum* reads with a sense of real urgency and concern.

Laudate Deum's [Praise God] continuity with its predecessor is indicated by its title, *Laudato Si'* (Praise be to you). Pope Francis states clearly that the title of this letter is “Praise God” because “when human beings claim to take God’s place, they become their own worst enemies” (LD 73). In the opening verse of *Laudate Deum*, Pope Francis, as in *Laudato Si'*, draws on the inspiration of St. Francis of Assisi, who praised God through his life, words and actions. He asks us to draw inspiration from “the message that St. Francis of Assisi proclaimed by his life, his canticles and all his actions” (LD 1).

A “Structural Sin”

Pope Francis describes climate change as a “structural sin” (LD 3). He agrees with the African bishops, that climate change “makes manifest ‘a tragic and striking example of structural sin’” (LD 3). According to him, “climate change is one of the principal challenges facing society and the global community” (LD 3). It is an issue “intimately related to the dignity of human life” (LD 3). He argues that “the effects of climate change are borne by the most vulnerable people, whether at home or around the world” (LD 3). His concern about climate change “goes beyond a merely ecological approach, because “our care for one another and our care for the earth are intimately bound together” (LD 3). He refutes various arguments against climate action

and the types of climate action that we undertake. He criticises people who downplay or deny outright the severity of the threat posed by climate change. Therefore, he says, “I feel obliged to make these clarifications, which may appear obvious, because of certain dismissive and scarcely reasonable opinions that I encounter, even within the Catholic Church” (LD 4).

A Universal Issue that Affects Everyone

Pope Francis speaks of the global climate crisis, stating that “despite all attempts to deny, conceal, gloss over or relativise the issue, the signs of climate change are here and increasingly evident” (LD 5). He observes that “in recent years we have witnessed extreme weather phenomena, frequent periods of unusual heat, drought and other cries of protest on the part of the earth” (LD 5), a “silent disease that affects everyone” (LD 5). He also highlights how it is “verifiable that specific climate changes provoked by humanity are notably heightening the probability of extreme phenomena that are increasingly frequent and intense” (LD 5). He underscores numerous extreme weather events as unmistakable signs of a planet in distress. According to him, a 0.5 degree Celsius increase in global temperature has already resulted in significant rises in floods, rains, droughts, heatwaves, and snowfall (LD 5). As we approach a 1.5 degrees Celsius increase, these events will become even more frequent and intense (LD 5). Beyond a 2 degrees Celsius increase, “the icecaps of Greenland and a large part of Antarctica will melt completely, with immensely grave consequences for everyone,” he warns (LD 5).

Pope Francis also replies to those who “have chosen to deride these facts” (LD 6), saying that we are “experiencing an unusual acceleration of warming, at such a speed that it will take only one generation – not centuries or millennia – in order to verify it” (LD 6). Extreme colds, too, are “alternative expressions of the same cause” (LD 7). He warns us that “probably in a few years many populations will have to move their homes because of these facts” (LD 6).

Pope Francis does not fail to emphasize how the poor and the most vulnerable suffer most from the consequences of climate change, even though they are less responsible for it. “In an attempt to simplify reality,” he writes, “there are those who would place responsibility on the poor, since they have many children, and even attempt to resolve the problem by mutilating women in less developed countries” (LD 9). He continues, “as usual, it would seem that everything is the fault of the poor. Yet the reality

is that a low, richer percentage of the planet contaminates more than the poorest 50% of the total world population and that per capita emissions of the richer countries are much greater than those of the poorer ones” (LD 9). He asks, “how can we forget that Africa, home to more than half of the world’s poorest people, is responsible for a minimal portion of historic emissions?” (LD 9).

Pope Francis challenges those who say efforts to mitigate climate change by reducing the use of fossil fuels “will lead to a reduction in the number of jobs” (LD 10). What is happening, according to Pope Francis, is that “millions of people are losing their jobs due to different effects of climate change: rising sea levels, droughts and other phenomena affecting the planet have left many people adrift” (LD 10). At the same time, he argues, “the transition to renewable forms of energy, properly managed” is capable of “generating countless jobs in different sectors” (LD 10).

Pope Francis emphatically reiterates that “it is no longer possible to doubt the human – “anthropic” – origin of climate change” (LD 11) and observes an advancement of the “technocratic paradigm,” that he already mentioned in *Laudato Si’*, which “consists in thinking as if reality, goodness and truth automatically flow from technological and economic power as such” (LD 20). He argues that “the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere ... was stable until the nineteenth century ... In the past fifty years, this increase has accelerated significantly” (LD 11).

Pope Francis expresses fear of what will happen if we reach 1.5 degrees or 2 degrees of warming. Referring to recent data and studies, he strongly reaffirms the human origin of climate change, which can no longer be doubted. According to him, over the past 50 years, a dramatic acceleration of greenhouse gases has been observed: “the temperature has risen at an unprecedented speed, greater than any time over the past two thousand years. In this period, the trend was a warming of 0.15° C per decade, double that of the last 150 years [...] At this rate, it is possible that in just ten years we will reach the recommended maximum global ceiling of 1.5°” (LD 12).

According to Pope Francis, “It is not possible to conceal” (LD 13) the correlation between these events and the growth of greenhouse gas emissions. He writes, “Regrettably, the climate crisis is not exactly a matter that interests the great economic powers, whose concern is with the greatest profit possible at minimal cost and in the shortest amount of time” (LD13).

He thinks that this pursuit of the greatest profit possible at minimum cost makes caring for our common home impossible.

Pope Francis repeatedly reminds us that we are already too late to respond adequately to the climate crisis. According to him, “some effects of the climate crisis are already irreversible, at least for several hundred years” (LD 15). He says that “the increase in the global temperature of the oceans” (LD 15) is just one example of climate degradation wrought by our human hands. He further says, “this is one of the many signs that the other creatures of this world have stopped being our companions along the way and have become instead our victims” (LD 15). He further argues that it will not be possible to “halt the enormous damage we have caused. We barely have time to prevent even more tragic damage” (LD 16).

Pope Francis argues that “certain apocalyptic diagnoses may well appear scarcely reasonable or insufficiently grounded”, but “we cannot state with certainty” what is going to happen (LD 17). He states, gently, “some effects of the climate crisis are already irreversible” (LD 15) and that “we are approaching a critical point ... there is no turning back.” (LD 17). Therefore, he argues, “a broader perspective is urgently needed ... What is being asked of us is nothing other than a certain responsibility for the legacy we will leave behind, once we pass from this world” (LD 18). Recalling the experience of the Covid-19 pandemic, Pope Francis repeats that “everything is connected and no one is saved alone” (LD 19).

A Paradigm that Fosters Ethical Decadence

Recalling his own earlier treatment of the technocratic paradigm in *Laudato Si'* (LD 20), Pope Francis talks about the technocratic paradigm, which continues to wreak havoc in society (LD 21). “Artificial intelligence and the latest technological innovations start with the notion of a human being with no limits, whose abilities and possibilities can be infinitely expanded thanks to technology,” he says (LD 21). He argues that “in this way, the technocratic paradigm monstrously feeds upon itself” (LD 21). Citing *Laudato Si'*, he claims, “Deep down, it consists in thinking “as if reality, goodness and truth automatically flow from technological and economic power as such” (LD 20; cf. LS 105). As a logical consequence, it then becomes easy “to accept the idea of infinite or unlimited growth, which proves so attractive to economists, financiers and experts in technology” (LD 20; cf. LS 106).

Pope Francis is not against the advancement of technology, although they may well be damaging as such, but about an ideology, what he calls in

other places throwaway culture, a manifestation of the broader culture of death. According to him “the greater problem is the ideology underlying an obsession: to increase human power beyond anything imaginable, before which nonhuman reality is a mere resource at its disposal” (LD 22). He further says, “everything that exists ceases to be a gift for which we should be thankful, esteem and cherish, and instead becomes a slave, prey to any whim of the human mind and its capacities” (LD 22). The Pope also warns of how humanity has never “had such power over itself, yet nothing ensures that it will be used wisely, particularly when we consider how it is currently being used It is extremely risky for a small part of humanity to have it” (LD 23).

According to Pope Francis, “not every increase in power represents progress for humanity.” He asks us to reflect upon the “admirable” technologies that were employed to decimate populations, drop atomic bombs and annihilate ethnic groups” (LD 24). His voice becomes very strong when he says, “we stand naked and exposed in the face of our ever-increasing power, lacking the wherewithal to control it” (LD 24). He reaffirms that “the world that surrounds us is not an object of exploitation, unbridled use and unlimited ambition” (LD 25). According to him, the “technological paradigm” makes the earth nothing more than a warehouse of resources, a “mere setting” for us (LD 25). Whereas, “we are, part of nature” (LD 25). “Human life, intelligence and freedom are elements of the nature that enriches our planet, part of its internal workings and its equilibrium” (LD 26). Therefore, this “excludes the idea that the human being is extraneous, a foreign element capable only of harming the environment. Human beings must be recognized as a part of nature” (LD 26).

In this context, Pope Francis calls us “to rethink among other things the question of human power, its meaning and its limits” (LD 28). He says, “We have made impressive and awesome technological advances, and we have not realized that at the same time, we have turned into highly dangerous beings, capable of threatening the lives of many beings and our own survival” (LD 28). Thus, he stresses that nature is not a resource to be exploited without end and urges us to recognize that unbridled ambition is not ethically sustainable (LD 28).

Pope Francis is concerned about the ethical decadence of power. He says, “the ethical decadence of real power is disguised thanks to marketing and false information, useful tools in the hands of those with greater

resources to employ them to shape public opinion” (LD 29). This happens when plans are made to undertake a project involving significant changes in the environment or high levels of contamination, “one raises the hopes of the people of that area by speaking of the local progress that it will be able to generate [...] Yet in reality there does not seem to be any true interest in the future of these people, since they are not clearly told that the project will result in the clearing of their lands, a decline in the quality of their lives” (LD 29).

According to Pope Francis, the “mentality of maximum gain at minimal cost disguised in terms of reasonableness, progress and illusory promises, makes impossible any sincere concern for our common home and any real preoccupation about assisting the poor and the needy discarded by our society” (LD 31). There exists, then, “rule by those born with greater possibilities and advantages” (32). He invites these individuals to ask themselves, “with an eye to the children who will pay for the harm done by their actions” (LD 33), what the meaning of their life is: “What is the meaning of my life? What is the meaning of my time on this earth? And what is the ultimate meaning of all my work and effort?” (LD 33).

Multilateralism from Below

Pope Francis addresses the weakness of international politics in handling the climate crisis. He laments the lack of cooperation between countries to address the climate crisis, even though successful efforts on past international concerns offer a helpful model. As a solution, he suggests to foster “multilateral agreements between States” (LD 34). However, according to him, multilateralism should not be seen as a “world authority concentrated in one person or in an elite with excessive power” (LD 35). He explains that “when we talk about the possibility of some form of world authority regulated by law, we need not necessarily think of a personal authority” (LD 35) but of “more effective world organizations, equipped with the power to provide for the global common good, the elimination of hunger and poverty and the sure defence of fundamental human rights” (LD 35). These, he says, “must be endowed with real authority, in such a way as to provide for the attainment of certain essential goals” (LD 35).

Pope Francis criticizes that “global crises are being squandered when they could be the occasions to bring about beneficial changes. This is what happened in the 2007-2008 financial crisis and again in the Covid-19 crisis” (LD 36), which led to “greater individualism, less integration and increased

freedom for the truly powerful, who always find a way to escape unscathed” (LD 36). He argues that multilateralism must take into account the new global situation and also recognises that “many groups and organisations within civil society help to compensate for the shortcomings of the international community, its lack of coordination in complex situations, and its lack of attention to fundamental human rights” (LD 37). He believes that “civil society with its organizations is capable of creating effective dynamics that the United Nations cannot” (LD 37). Therefore, he says that “more than saving the old multilateralism, it appears that the current challenge is to reconfigure and recreate it, taking into account the new world situation” (LD 37). For this reason, he reiterates that “unless citizens control political power – national, regional and municipal – it will not be possible to control damage to the environment” (LD 38).

Having affirmed the primacy and dignity of the human person, Pope Francis explains that “it is not a matter of replacing politics, but of recognizing that the emerging forces are becoming increasingly relevant” (LD 40). “The very fact,” he says, “that answers to problems can come from any country, however little, ends up presenting multilateralism as an inevitable process” (LD 40). Here, he calls for “multilateral diplomacy” (LD 41). This would be based on the representation of all the stakeholders who occupy the space of the earth, especially those who are often marginalised, and who don’t have a ‘voice’ at all. What Pope Francis is suggesting is a multilateralism “from below and not simply one determined by the elites of power” (LD 42). He stresses the need to have a “different framework for effective cooperation, as it is urgent to respond to new problems and to react with global mechanisms to the environmental, public health, cultural and social challenges” (LD 42). Further, he says “all this presupposes the development of a new procedure for decision-making and legitimising those decisions” and “spaces for conversation, consultation, arbitration, conflict resolution and supervision, and, in the end, a sort of increased ‘democratisation’ in the global context, so that the various situations can be expressed and included” (LD 43). “In this framework, there would necessarily be required spaces for conversation, consultation, arbitration, conflict resolution and supervision[...].” (LD 43). It may not be helpful, he writes, “for us to support institutions in order to preserve the rights of the more powerful without caring for those of all” (LD 43).

Looking Ahead with Hope

In the fourth Chapter, Pope Francis reflects upon the progress and failures of climate conferences and encourages us to overcome the selfish positions of countries for the benefit of the global common good (cf. LD 44, 52). He shares the progress and disappointments related to the various climate conferences, starting from the 1992 Rio de Janeiro Conference, which led to the adoption of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), to the COP27 in Sharm El Sheikh (LD 44). He recalls the one in Paris, an agreement that came into effect in November 2016. He says, although “a binding agreement, not all its dispositions are obligations in the strict sense, and some of them leave ample room for discretion” (LD 47).

Pope Francis mentions his disappointment with the Madrid COP and recalls that the Glasgow COP revived the Paris goals, with many recommendations. According to him, during these years, there was “an abundance of recommendations whose actual effect was hardly foreseeable. Proposals tending to ensure a rapid and effective transition to alternative and less polluting forms of energy made no progress” (LD 49). According to him the conference held in Egypt “was one more example of the difficulty of negotiations” (LD 51). Despite the steps forward in consolidating a system for financing “loss and damage” in countries most affected by climate disasters, “too, many points remained imprecise, above all the concrete responsibility of the countries that have to contribute” (LD 51). Therefore, Francis urges for new and “suitable mechanisms for oversight, periodic review and penalties in cases of noncompliance” (LD 52).

Despite the gravity and urgency of the situation we face, Pope Francis tells us that we must continue to hope. Looking ahead to COP 28 in Dubai, Pope Francis writes that “to say that there is nothing to hope for would be suicidal, for it would mean exposing all humanity, especially the poorest, to the worst impacts of climate change” (LD 53). At the same time, he underlines how “we must move beyond the mentality of appearing to be concerned but not having the courage needed to produce substantial changes” (LD 56). He says that this conference can be a “change of direction” (LD 54). We must, says the Pope, “keep hoping that COP28 will allow for a decisive acceleration of energy transition, with effective commitments subject to ongoing monitoring. However, this Conference can represent a change of direction” (LD 54).

Pope Francis reminds us that “despite the many negotiations and agreements, global emissions continue to increase” (LD 55). He argues that humans can always change and humans have collaborated successfully in the past, thinking specifically of the repair to the ozone layer” (LD 55). However, he observes that “the necessary transition towards clean energy sources such as wind and solar energy, and the abandonment of fossil fuels, is not progressing at the necessary speed. Consequently, whatever is being done risks being seen only as a ploy to distract attention” (LD 55).

According to Pope Francis, we cannot search merely for a technological solution to our problems, for he says, “we risk remaining trapped in the mindset of pasting and papering over cracks, while beneath the surface there is a continuing deterioration to which we continue to contribute” (57). Therefore, he hopes that COP28 will bring “binding forms of energy transition that meet three conditions: that they are efficient, obligatory and readily monitored” (LD 59).

Pope Francis asks the participants of COP 28 in Dubai to “demonstrate the nobility of politics and not its shame.” (LD 60). He calls on those attending COP28 to think in terms of the common good and the future generations (LD 60). He sets before them this question to reflect upon: “What would induce anyone, at this stage, to hold on to power, only to be remembered for their inability to take action when it was urgent and necessary to do so?” (LD 60).

The World Sings of an Infinite Love

In the last chapter, “Spiritual Motivations,” Pope Francis calls upon people of all religious confessions to respond to the care for our common home. He says, “Authentic faith not only gives strength to the human heart, but also transforms life, transfigures our goals and sheds light on our relationship to others and with creation as a whole” (LD 61). He particularly draws the attention of the Catholic faithful: “I cannot fail in this regard to remind the Catholic faithful of the motivations born of their faith” (LD 61). He also extends this invitation to all: “my brothers and sisters of other religions to do the same” (LD 61).

Pope Francis explains the beauty and goodness of God’s creation and our responsibility to care for it. According to him, to praise God the Creator, we must recognize our role in the climate crisis and hold ourselves responsible for our impact on all creation: “God saw everything that he had made, and indeed, it was very good” (Gen 1:31). His is “the earth with all

that is in it” (Deut 10:14). For this reason, he tells us that, “the land shall not be sold in perpetuity, for the land is mine; with me you are but aliens and tenants” (Lev 25:23)” (LD 62). Citing *Laudato Si*, he further writes: “responsibility for God’s earth means that human beings, endowed with intelligence, must respect the laws of nature and the delicate equilibria existing between the creatures of this world” (LD 62).

Pope Francis asks us to see the inherent beauty of God’s creation: “If ‘the universe unfolds in God, who fills it completely ... there is a mystical meaning to be found in a leaf, in a mountain trail, in a dewdrop, in a poor person’s face” (LD 65). Further, he reminds us of the foundational question, “the world sings of an infinite Love: how can we fail to care for it?” (LD 65). He contends that “God has united us to all his creatures. Nonetheless, the technocratic paradigm can isolate us from the world that surrounds us and deceive us by making us forget that the entire world is a “contact zone” (LD 66). While recognizing the “peculiar and central value of the human being in the midst of the marvellous concert of all beings” (LD 67), he also believes that “human life is incomprehensible and unsustainable without other creatures” (LD 67). He believes that “as part of the universe, all of us are linked by unseen bonds and together form a kind of universal family, a sublime communion which fills us with a sacred, affectionate and humble respect” (LD 67). According to him, “this is not a product of our own will; its origin lies elsewhere, in the depths of our being” because “God has joined us so closely to the world around us that we can feel the desertification of the soil almost as a physical ailment, and the extinction of a species as a painful disfigurement” (LD 68). Therefore, he asks us to “stop thinking, [...] of human beings as autonomous, omnipotent and limitless, and begin to think of ourselves differently, in a humbler but more fruitful way” (LD 68).

Pope Francis invites all of us “to accompany a pilgrimage of reconciliation with the world that is our home and to help make it more beautiful because that commitment has to do with our personal dignity and highest values” (LD 69). He underlines both the individual and collective role in this process of reconciliation. He says, “the most effective solutions will not come from individual efforts alone, but above all from major political decisions on the national and international level” (LD 69). Therefore, he invites us to have “a path of reconciliation with the world that shelters us, and to embellish it with our own contribution” (LD 69).

What is important, Pope Francis writes, is to remember that “there are no lasting changes without cultural changes, without a maturing of lifestyles and convictions within societies, and there are no cultural changes without personal changes” (LD 70). He affirms that “a broad change in the irresponsible lifestyle connected with the Western model would have a significant long-term impact. As a result, along with indispensable political decisions, we would be making progress along the way to genuine care for one another” (LD 72). Finally, he asks us to understand our identity and not to assume the role of the creator: “When human beings claim to take God’s place, they become their own worst enemies” (LD 73).

Conclusion

The climate crisis is an undeniable reality. *Laudate Deum* is a clarion call to tackle the climate crisis, recognising that time is running out. It offers insights into the current state of the global climate crisis, and the inadequacies of current responses, and proposes the way forward. It addresses to “all people of good will on the climate crisis,” admonishing the human family that has neglected its relationships with creation, one another, and above all, God. It emphasizes the anthropogenic origin of climate change and the irreversible nature of many associated catastrophes. While recognizing the limitations in rectifying the damage done to nature, it underscores the importance of taking measures to prevent further harm. It is a prophetic call to ecological conversion.

In *Laudate Deum*, Pope Francis expresses hope that we, as individuals and societies, can reduce the negative human impact on the natural environment, and create a better environment for future generations. He invites us for a “pilgrimage of reconciliation,” “reconciliation with the world that shelters us” (LD 69). He believes that the global environmental crisis strongly affects not only the indigenous peoples, the poor, and endangered species, but also the future of all young people (LD 8). He reminds us that “we are all connected” (LD 19) and “no one is saved alone” (LD 19), and therefore, he invites us to walk in “communion and commitment,” (LD 66-67) together, synodically. Thus, *Laudate Deum* stands as Pope Francis’ prophetic call in response to the climate crisis.

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¹ All the references from the Apostolic Exhortation *Laudate Deum* are from Pope Francis, *Laudate Deum: Apostolic Exhortation of the Holy Father Francis* (Mumbai: St. Pauls, 2023). Hereinafter the Exhortation will be abbreviated as LD with numbers from the Apostolic Exhortation.